

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CURRENT STATE OF THE USE OF MODERN MONITORING AND EVALUATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Aslanova G.,

Ganja State University "Pedagogy and methodology of education" teacher of the department

Isgandarova R.,

Ganja State University "Pedagogy and methodology of education" teacher of the department

Mammadova V.

Ganja State University "Pedagogy and methodology of education" teacher of the department

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0987-4198>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754184>

Abstract

In the modern era, highly educated professional personnel form the foundation of a country's intellectual potential in the education system. In the higher education system, in order to cultivate a well-rounded individual—one who possesses comprehensive knowledge, skills, habits, and abilities; is independent in thinking; and upholds national, moral, and ethical values—it becomes necessary to develop new approaches to teaching and training, monitoring the activities of higher education institutions, evaluating the performance of staff, and assessing students' achievements in the learning process. Monitoring in the education system reveals that, as stated in the "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan" (2013), the role of newly emerging reforms is not limited to merely shaping the knowledge and skills acquired by students. The knowledge and skills obtained in the educational process, as well as ethical and moral norms and values, create the necessary conditions for each student to become a worthy member of society. These qualities enable them to become exemplary colleagues through their knowledge and ethical behavior, responsible family members, and model citizens.

Keywords: Monitoring, quality, educational, knowledge, teaching

On the Approval of the Education Reform Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Based on the decree of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, a new stage of development in the field of education has begun. The main principle of the education reforms carried out in our republic was the creation of a secular education system and making the education process its main focus. The implementation of these reforms serves to improve the quality of education in the country and integrate the national education system into the global education system. Therefore, mechanisms must be established to conduct monitoring and comprehensive evaluations in the field of education. Monitoring and evaluation serve as a control function for quality development. Regular observations aimed at improving quality must be conducted, and positive trends during the transition phase should always be tracked. Monitoring and evaluation can be considered tools for measuring the quality of the pedagogical process and its individual aspects.

To make the goals of the applied education system and educational institutions a reality, it is essential to solve the following key issues: strengthening the regulatory framework, ensuring the effective use of collected data, utilizing new educational content, aligning the level of preparedness with the demands of market relations, employing a new economic model to ensure the efficiency of learning systems, and scientifically substantiating new approaches and methods in the teaching process. In accordance with the requirements of modern education models, teacher training should also be a priority. These approaches, in turn, require a more objective assessment of the quality of education

outcomes, observation of the education system, and implementation of new evaluation mechanisms in the teaching process. [5]

The assessment of students' knowledge, skills, and competencies within the classroom is conducted based on the following criteria:

- ❖ The results of tests determining the actual level of knowledge and skills;
- ❖ The conscious application of knowledge and skills in practical activities;
- ❖ The level of studying textbooks and supplementary literature related to the subject;
- ❖ The degree of independence and creative approach to work;
- ❖ The completion level of homework assignments;
- ❖ Adherence to safety regulations during practical tasks.

The internal school assessment of students' knowledge and skills is carried out based on the guidelines prepared and sent to schools by the Ministry of Education. Despite effective work being done in recent years to improve the evaluation system—such as tracking the development dynamics of students' grades, conducting qualifying exams in upper grades, organizing seminars, administering periodic test questions, and checking written assignments—the existing traditional assessment methods do not allow for an objective evaluation of students' academic achievements. This is because traditional assessments rely on calculating an average of current grades to determine final scores. This gradually hinders students' development, discouraging

them from acquiring deeper and broader knowledge and skills in the long run. As a result, assessment loses its formative function, and students become more inclined to focus on learning only the easily understandable parts of a topic rather than gaining a complete understanding of it.

It has been determined that the shortcomings and deficiencies in the existing grading system, which has been used in schools for a long time and is well understood by teachers, can be eliminated by applying formative (formative) assessment methods. Unlike summative assessment, formative assessment provides students with the opportunity to revisit and improve their knowledge. In other words, students who have not learned or have weakly grasped certain materials can review them again during the final weeks of the semester or academic year and improve their grades. Formative assessment can be conducted through oral and written tests on learned topics and sections, assigning research papers on specific subjects, and engaging students in creative projects. [6]

In recent years, the implementation of quality management and monitoring assessment systems in higher education institutions in Azerbaijan has been closely linked to the future governance of the country. For this reason, the development of education and the improvement of quality have always been publicized and mutually analyzed. Until recently, no program or methodological approach was developed regarding the creation of positive trends in education through the application of monitoring and assessment systems. However, in the current period, the education system has become more developed and relevant.

Analyzed pedagogical experience shows that some specialists believe that the real educational outcomes of higher education institutions are necessary only for universities, industry leaders, and the parents of students. However, such views in the field of education can lead to misdirection of education outcomes. It should be noted that life itself shapes this direction. The improvement of education quality must be developed in connection with real life. It should be remembered that schools alone cannot fully meet the demands of social stakeholders. Today, the main goal of higher education institutions should be to prepare students for modern life. [7]

As stated in the educational concepts and state programs adopted in our country, improving the quality of higher education, implementing assessment and monitoring mechanisms, and comparing our education system with the higher education institutions of other countries hold primary importance. To achieve these goals, higher education institutions must first define their objectives, clearly establish their tasks in accordance with these objectives, and organize their work within an operational program that enables them to meet the needs of social stakeholders, students, and their parents.

The primary direction of modernizing all educational institutions in our country is to improve the quality of teaching, education, and upbringing processes in schools. Conducting regular monitoring and evaluation

mechanisms in schools is one of the essential conditions for achieving this. From this, we can conclude that achieving high-quality education is closely related to the management of the pedagogical process.

In an era of rapid information flow, the most important factor for improving the quality of education, training, and teaching processes is the regular implementation of monitoring and evaluation in schools and the use of new methods in these processes. The key criteria for the monitoring and evaluation mechanism include the proper development of its parameters, indicators, and content. The main objectives of the monitoring and evaluation mechanism are not only to correct the results of the given process but also to track and make necessary adjustments to its positive and negative changes in real-time. [7]

Achieving quality in education requires implementing the following processes:

- ✓ Creating a democratic education system by ensuring quality at all levels of education;

- ✓ Taking into account students' personal qualities and interests to create an individualized education process using various educational programs from different institutions;

- ✓ Establishing a competitive education system based on the quality of educational programs and services in the country;

- ✓ Developing modern education programs that meet the personal and diverse characteristics of students in educational institutions;

- ✓ Organizing training across all educational fields.

The quality of monitoring and evaluation in education is determined by the consistency and objectivity of the information used. The collected data should be promptly delivered to education experts for decision-making. Therefore, the dissemination of information is a key focus in the implementation of monitoring and evaluation.

In summary, monitoring and evaluation in higher education institutions, as well as in every educational institution, should be meticulously planned while considering relevant factors. The quality assurance process should be continuously monitored, ensuring that high educational standards are maintained. Only then can we talk about achieving high-quality education.

Ramiz Mammadzadeh, in his book *"Quality in Education as a Leading Direction,"* discusses the importance of assessment and highlights that the results of the educational process must be clearly measured and defined. He states that educational measurement involves evaluating specific operational characteristics and ensuring an objective approach to assessing learning outcomes. [8]

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